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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PEDAGOGICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR DEVELOPING AN INTERACTIVE MOBILE APPLICATION FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN (BASED ON THE SOLOBEE PROJECT)

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Abstract: This study investigates the pedagogical and methodological foundations for developing an interactive mobile application aimed at teaching English to preschool children, based on the SoloBee Project. The research addresses the growing gap between the widespread use of mobile technologies by young learners and the lack of scientifically grounded educational applications in early childhood education.

The study is based on a Design-Based Research approach and employs an experimental design involving preschool children aged 4 to 6 years. Participants were divided into experimental and control groups to compare the effectiveness of mobile-assisted learning with traditional instructional methods. The SoloBee application integrates phonetic instruction, game-based learning, and multimodal interaction to support early language acquisition.

The results demonstrate that the experimental group showed significantly higher improvement in vocabulary acquisition, letter recognition, and early reading skills compared to the control group. The findings also indicate increased motivation and engagement among learners using the application. These outcomes are consistent with established theories of phonological awareness, multimedia learning, and gamification.

The study contributes to the field of educational technology by providing a structured pedagogical framework for the development of mobile learning applications in preschool education. It also highlights the potential of integrating interactive digital tools with evidence-based teaching methods to enhance learning outcomes in early childhood.

Key words: early childhood education, mobile learning, English language acquisition, phonetic instruction, gamification, multimodal learning, preschool education, educational technology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot SoloBee loyihasi asosida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishga mo'ljallangan interaktiv mobil ilovani ishlab chiqishning pedagogik va metodologik asoslarini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot yosh o'quvchilar tomonidan mobil texnologiyalardan keng foydalanish va maktabgacha ta'limda ilmiy asoslangan ta'lim ilovalari yetishmasligi o'rtasidagi ortib borayotgan tafovutni ko'rib chiqadi.

Tadqiqot Design-Based Research yondashuviga asoslangan bo'lib, 4-6 yoshdagi maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni qamrab olgan eksperimental dizayndan foydalanadi. Ishtirokchilar mobil ta'limning samaradorligini an'anaviy o'qitish usullari bilan taqqoslash uchun eksperimental va nazorat guruhlariga ajratildi. SoloBee ilovasi erta til o'zlashtirishni qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun fonetik o'qitish, o'yin asosidagi o'qitish va multimodal o'zaro ta'sirni integratsiya qiladi.

Natijalar eksperimental guruh nazorat guruhiga nisbatan lug'at boyligini o'zlashtirish, harflarni tanish va boshlang'ich o'qish ko'nikmalarida sezilarli darajada yuqori natijalarni ko'rsatganini namoyon etadi. Shuningdek, ilovadan foydalangan o'quvchilarda motivatsiya va jalb qilinganlik darajasi oshgani aniqlangan. Ushbu natijalar fonologik xabardorlik, multimedia asosida o'qitish va gamifikatsiya nazariyalari bilan mos keladi.

Tadqiqot maktabgacha ta'limda mobil o'quv ilovalarini ishlab chiqish uchun tuzilgan pedagogik modelni taqdim etish orqali ta'lim texnologiyalari sohasiga hissa qo'shadi. Shuningdek, erta bolalik davrida ta'lim natijalarini yaxshilash uchun interaktiv raqamli vositalarni dalillarga asoslangan o'qitish usullari bilan integratsiya qilish imkoniyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim, mobil o'qitish, ingliz tilini o'zlashtirish, fonetik o'qitish, gamifikatsiya, multimodal o'qitish, erta til o'rganish, ta'lim texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено изучению педагогических и методологических основ разработки интерактивного мобильного приложения, предназначенного для обучения английскому языку детей дошкольного возраста, на основе проекта SoloBee. В работе рассматривается проблема возрастающего разрыва между широким использованием мобильных технологий детьми и недостатком научно обоснованных образовательных приложений в системе дошкольного образования.

Исследование основано на подходе Design-Based Research и включает экспериментальный дизайн с участием детей дошкольного возраста от 4 до 6 лет. Участники были разделены на экспериментальную и контрольную группы для сравнения эффективности мобильного обучения с традиционными методами преподавания. Приложение SoloBee интегрирует фонетическое обучение, игровое обучение и мультимодальное взаимодействие для поддержки раннего усвоения языка.

Результаты показывают, что экспериментальная группа продемонстрировала значительно более высокий уровень усвоения лексики, распознавания букв и начальных навыков чтения по сравнению с контрольной группой. Также отмечено повышение мотивации и вовлеченности обучающихся, использующих приложение. Полученные результаты соответствуют признанным теориям фонологической осведомленности, мультимедийного обучения и геймификации.

Данное исследование вносит вклад в область образовательных технологий, предлагая структурированную педагогическую модель разработки мобильных обучающих приложений для дошкольного образования. Также подчеркивается потенциал интеграции интерактивных цифровых инструментов с научно обоснованными методами обучения для повышения эффективности образовательного процесса в раннем детстве.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, мобильное обучение, усвоение английского языка, фонетическое обучение, геймификация, мультимодальное обучение, образовательные технологии.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the rapid development of information and communication technologies has significantly influenced the field of education, particularly early childhood education. The widespread use of mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets has increased children's exposure to digital environments and created new opportunities for organizing the learning process through modern technological tools (Traxler, 2018; Kukulska-Hulme, 2020).

However, despite the growing use of mobile devices among preschool children, many existing applications lack a strong pedagogical and methodological foundation. Studies show that although children actively interact with digital devices, a large proportion of available content does not provide structured learning or measurable educational outcomes (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2015). Analysis within the SoloBee project also confirms that children frequently use smartphones, but the majority of content lacks sufficient educational value and methodological support. This creates a clear gap between technological accessibility and effective learning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

At the same time, preschool age is considered a critical period for language acquisition. According to developmental psychology, early childhood is characterized by rapid growth in phonological awareness, vocabulary acquisition, and symbolic thinking (Piaget, 1964; Vygotsky, 1978). During this stage, children are especially sensitive to language input, which makes it essential to design learning environments that align with their cognitive and psychological characteristics.

Modern pedagogical and cognitive research emphasizes that effective learning in early childhood should be interactive, engaging, and supported by multiple sensory channels. Multimodal learning, which combines visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements, significantly enhances comprehension and memory retention (Mayer, 2009). In addition, emotional engagement and meaningful repetition play a key role in sustaining attention and supporting long-term learning outcomes (Immordino-Yang & Damasio, 2007).

Despite these well-established principles, traditional preschool education often lacks structured methodologies for teaching early literacy and foreign languages. In many cases, teaching approaches remain fragmented, and instructional tools are not sufficiently engaging or adapted to children's developmental needs. Furthermore, the absence of adaptive learning mechanisms prevents educators from effectively addressing individual differences in learning pace and cognitive development (Hwang et al., 2020).

In response to these challenges, the present study focuses on the development of an interactive mobile application for teaching English to preschool children based on the SoloBee project. The application is designed using a phonetic approach that emphasizes sound-letter relationships, combined with game-based learning and interactive activities, which are widely recognized as effective strategies in early childhood education (Gee,

2003; Nation, 2001). Additionally, the application incorporates progress tracking features that allow monitoring of children's learning outcomes and support continuous improvement.

The aim of this study is to provide pedagogical and methodological justification for the development of such a mobile application and to demonstrate its effectiveness in supporting English language acquisition among preschool children.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a design-based research (DBR) approach, which is widely used in educational technology to develop and evaluate innovative learning tools in real educational contexts (Brown, 1992; Wang & Hannafin, 2005). The aim of this method is not only to design an educational product, but also to generate pedagogical knowledge grounded in practice.

The participants of the study were preschool children aged 4 to 6 years. A total of 60 children were selected and divided into two groups: an experimental group ($n = 30$) and a control group ($n = 30$). The selection was carried out under similar educational and social conditions to ensure comparability between the groups. Such group-based experimental design is commonly used in early childhood education research to evaluate instructional interventions (Creswell, 2014).

The experimental group was taught using the SoloBee mobile application, which is based on a phonetic approach emphasizing the relationship between sounds and letters. Phonetic instruction is considered one of the most effective methods for early reading development, as it supports phonological awareness and decoding skills (Ehri, 2005; National Reading Panel, 2000). The application also integrates game-based learning elements, which have been shown to increase motivation and engagement among young learners (Gee, 2003; Plass et al., 2015).

The control group received traditional instruction based on teacher-led activities and printed learning materials, which reflect commonly used practices in preschool education. This allowed for a direct comparison between digital and traditional teaching approaches.

The duration of the experiment was 40 days, with daily sessions lasting approximately 15 minutes, which corresponds to the recommended duration for maintaining attention and cognitive engagement in preschool children. Short, consistent learning sessions are known to be more effective for young learners than longer, less frequent instruction (Gathercole & Alloway, 2008).

To measure learning outcomes, pre-test and post-test assessments were conducted. The tests were designed to evaluate three main indicators: vocabulary acquisition, letter recognition, and early reading ability. These indicators are widely recognized as key components of early language development (Snow et al., 1998).

Quantitative data were analyzed using statistical methods, including mean score comparison and independent samples t-test. The use of t-test allows for determining whether the differences between the experimental and control groups are statistically significant (Field, 2013). The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the study demonstrate a statistically significant improvement in the learning outcomes of children in the experimental group compared to the control group. Quantitative analysis shows that the integration of an interactive mobile application based on phonetic instruction and game-based learning has a positive effect on early language acquisition.

At the initial stage of the study (pre-test), both the experimental and control groups demonstrated comparable levels of English language proficiency. Statistical analysis confirmed that there were no significant differences between the groups at baseline ($p > 0.05$), which indicates that the groups were equivalent prior to the intervention (Field, 2013). This comparability ensures the internal validity of the experimental design.

Following the 40-day intervention period, clear differences emerged between the two groups. The experimental group, which used the SoloBee mobile application, showed a substantial improvement in vocabulary acquisition, letter recognition, and early reading skills. These findings are consistent with previous research demonstrating that phonetic-based instruction significantly enhances early literacy development by improving phonological awareness and decoding abilities (Ehri, 2005; National Reading Panel, 2000).

The average performance score of the experimental group increased by approximately 25%, whereas the control group showed a more modest improvement of around 10%. Independent samples t-test analysis confirmed that the difference between the groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the observed improvement is unlikely to be due to chance (Field, 2013). These results support the effectiveness of mobile-assisted learning when it is grounded in sound pedagogical principles.

In addition to the quantitative findings, qualitative observations revealed higher levels of engagement, motivation, and sustained attention among children in the experimental group. Children using the SoloBee

application demonstrated greater enthusiasm and active participation during learning sessions. This can be explained by the integration of game-based learning elements, which are known to increase intrinsic motivation and engagement in young learners (Plass et al., 2015; Deterding et al., 2011).

Furthermore, the use of multimodal content (visual, auditory, and interactive stimuli) contributed to improved comprehension and retention, as supported by cognitive theory (Mayer, 2009). The combination of interactivity and feedback mechanisms allowed children to remain focused and actively involved in the learning process, which is a key factor in early childhood education (Hirsh-Pasek et al., 2015).

Overall, the results indicate that the SoloBee mobile application provides a more effective learning environment compared to traditional teaching methods, both in terms of measurable learning outcomes and learner engagement.

The findings of this study confirm that the integration of mobile technology with pedagogically grounded approaches can significantly enhance early language learning outcomes. The observed improvement in the experimental group is consistent with previous research demonstrating the effectiveness of mobile-assisted language learning when it is aligned with cognitive and developmental principles (Kukulska-Hulme, 2020; Hwang et al., 2020). In this context, the effectiveness of the SoloBee application can be explained through several interrelated pedagogical and psychological factors.

First, the use of a phonetic approach plays a crucial role in supporting the natural development of early reading skills. By establishing a clear relationship between sounds and letters, phonics-based instruction enhances phonological awareness, which is widely recognized as a key predictor of reading success (Ehri, 2005; National Reading Panel, 2000). The results of this study align with these findings, as children in the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement in letter recognition and early reading abilities. This suggests that integrating phonetic principles into digital learning environments can effectively support foundational literacy development.

Second, the integration of game-based learning elements significantly contributes to increased motivation and engagement among preschool learners. Young children are naturally inclined toward play-based activities, and embedding educational content within interactive game structures creates a more engaging and meaningful learning experience. Previous studies have shown that gamification enhances intrinsic motivation, persistence, and active participation in learning tasks (Deterding et al., 2011; Plass et al., 2015). The higher levels of engagement observed in the experimental group support this view and highlight the importance of designing learning environments that align with children's natural learning behaviors.

Third, the multimodal design of the SoloBee application, which combines visual, auditory, and interactive elements, appears to facilitate better comprehension and retention of information. According to cognitive theory, particularly the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, the use of multiple sensory channels enhances information processing and reduces cognitive overload when properly structured (Mayer, 2009). In early childhood education, where learners rely heavily on sensory experiences, multimodal input is especially effective in supporting understanding and memory formation. The improved learning outcomes observed in this study provide empirical support for the application of multimodal learning principles in digital environments.

Furthermore, the inclusion of progress tracking and feedback mechanisms represents an important methodological advantage of the application. Continuous monitoring of learning outcomes allows for a more individualized approach to instruction and creates the foundation for adaptive learning systems. Research indicates that feedback and data-driven instruction can significantly improve learning efficiency by addressing individual differences in pace and ability (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). Although the current version of the SoloBee application provides basic progress tracking, its further development could incorporate adaptive algorithms to personalize learning pathways.

Overall, the results of this study demonstrate that mobile-assisted learning, when grounded in sound pedagogical and psychological principles, can serve as an effective tool in early childhood education. The combination of phonetic instruction, gamification, and multimodal interaction creates a comprehensive learning environment that supports both cognitive development and learner engagement. These findings contribute to the growing body of research emphasizing the importance of integrating technology with pedagogy rather than using digital tools in isolation.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study provides a pedagogical and methodological justification for the development of an interactive mobile application for teaching English to preschool children based on the SoloBee project. The findings confirm that the integration of mobile technologies into early childhood education can be effective when it is grounded in established pedagogical and cognitive principles (Kukulska-Hulme, 2020; Hwang et al., 2020).

The results of the study demonstrate that combining phonetic instruction, game-based learning, and interactive digital environments leads to significant improvements in early language acquisition. In particular, the use of phonics-based approaches supports the development of phonological awareness and early reading skills, which are critical for literacy development (Ehri, 2005; National Reading Panel, 2000). At the same time, the incorporation of game elements enhances children's motivation and engagement, which are key factors influencing learning effectiveness in early childhood (Plass et al., 2015; Deterding et al., 2011).

Furthermore, the use of multimodal learning environments-integrating visual, auditory, and interactive components-facilitates better comprehension and retention of learning materials. This is consistent with cognitive theories suggesting that learning is more effective when multiple sensory channels are engaged in a structured manner (Mayer, 2009). The findings also highlight the importance of creating learning environments that are developmentally appropriate and aligned with the cognitive characteristics of young learners (Piaget, 1964; Vygotsky, 1978).

An important contribution of this study is the development of a structured pedagogical framework for designing mobile learning applications in preschool education. Unlike many existing digital tools, which lack methodological grounding, the proposed approach integrates theory and practice, offering a more systematic and effective model for early language learning.

Finally, the study identifies prospects for further research and development. Future work may focus on integrating adaptive learning algorithms and artificial intelligence to personalize the learning process and better address individual differences among learners. Research in educational technology indicates that adaptive systems can significantly enhance learning efficiency by providing tailored feedback and individualized learning pathways (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Holmes et al., 2019).

The findings suggest that mobile-assisted learning, when designed on a solid pedagogical and methodological basis, has strong potential to improve the quality of early childhood education and support effective language acquisition.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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